

Innovation Networks of Cork, Resins and Edibles in the Mediterranean basin - INCREDIBLE

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Structure of the document

This deliverable aims to list and to provide an overview of the main dissemination products that emerged from the communication activities of the thematic network INCREDIBLE. These activities, stemming from or developed to support tasks in WP 1, 2 and 3, and are intended to bring thematic network information and results to a wider audience beyond the extent of the thematic network in all fields (science, practice, business, policy and media).

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1. INCREDIBLE project brochure

A generic INCREDIBLE brochure includes general and introductory information for broad distribution. The target audience for this brochure is intentionally broad in scope so that it may appeal to the wider thematic network community and wider society, at local, regional, national and international scales. This includes potential stakeholders for the innovation networks (iNets) but also national bodies, forest authorities and regulatory bodies, NGOs, EU institutions, participants at technical and scientific meetings and conferences and other stakeholders. The content highlights the key main messages of the thematic network and its goals. The brochure is produced in digital format, in English, but consortium partners are encouraged to translate it into their own language.

https://incredibleforest.net/sites/default/files/resource/files/brochure_incredible_web.pdf

2. Final INCREDIBLE project brochure

An updated brochure with thematic network results and experiences has been developed at the end of the thematic network for distribution at the Final Conference, Policy Forum and other relevant events. The target audience for this brochure is the same as the generic brochure, broad in scope so that it may appeal to the wider thematic network community and wider society, at local, regional, national and international scales. The brochure is produced in digital format, in English, but consortium partners are encouraged to translate it into their own language.

https://www.incredibleforest.net/sites/default/files/resource/files/final_brochure_incredible_pdf.pdf

3. Templates for regional / iNet-specific communications activities

Templates and general content for regional / iNet-specific materials summarising scientific knowledge, innovative practices, relevant business models and social innovations were produced, in discussion with iNet coordinators.

These include event posters, event announcement templates, e-mail invitation templates, event agenda templates (in the long or short formats, depending on the type of event). iNet coordinators often choose to translate these materials in local languages for national-wide events, mainly the science to practice events.

<https://www.incredibleforest.net/content/incredible-templates>

4. Infographics

A series of infographics focus on the three cross-cutting topics identified for the cross-cutting innovation clinics:

1. Integrating NWFP in Territorial Marketing and Ecosystem Service value chains
2. Innovative business and entrepreneurship in NWFP sector
3. ITC tools for improved NWFP value chains and market intelligence

Infographics are focused on various relevant case studies and portray the seminar findings in a clear and accessible format, reflecting the participation of cross-cutting innovation clinics

attendees, drawing together cross-cutting issues from across the iNets and identifying key action points for NWFP producers, entrepreneurs and policy makers.

<https://incredibleforest.net/transversal-resources>

5. Motion infographics

Five motion infographics, one for each iNet, have been designed. They explain the relevance of the NWFP, the gaps in knowledge, the reasons for engagement in operational groups and other multi-actor networks, and how INCREDIBLE will contribute to co-generate possible solutions. These infographics have been broadcasted at the Final Conference event and are available at the INCREDIBLE website, located at each iNet section.

<https://incredibleforest.net/inet/cork>

<https://incredibleforest.net/inet/resins>

<https://incredibleforest.net/inet/aromatic-medicinal-plants>

<https://incredibleforest.net/inet/mushrooms-and-truffles>

<https://incredibleforest.net/inet/wild-nuts-and-berries>

6. INCREDIBLE newsletter

The INCREDIBLE newsletter is produced twice a year and includes blog updates, meetings, activities, research and new knowledge. It also highlights the main activities carried out in the thematic network during the preceding months. In addition to the newsletter, during the period when most the INCREDIBLE events took place, the events bulletin was also monthly published. It listed the upcoming events, with the agenda and the link to register. The newsletter and the events bulletin were disseminated via partners' networks, newsletter subscription, thematic network website and social media (in English).

<https://incredibleforest.net/newsletters>

7. Policy recommendations

The policy recommendations for NWFP issued by the thematic network have been developed through a collaborative process taking place within Task 3.3.

Three dissemination products have been developed in order to provide an orientation to policy makers and key stakeholders on NWFP.

White paper on NWFP

Started in summer 2019, the white paper (which complete title is *Non-wood forest products for people, nature and the green economy. Recommendations for policy priorities in Europe. A white paper based on lessons learned from around the Mediterranean*) provides an orientation to policy makers and key stakeholders on NWFP, presenting key themes for NWFP as well as policy recommendations to develop and order to enhance the potential of different value chains. Its final version was presented at the INCREDIBLE Policy Forum (March 2021) where participants had the opportunity to provide further inputs and revisions.

<https://incredibleforest.net/policy-recommendations>

<https://efi.int/publications-bank/k2a>

Policy key actions brochure

An updated brochure with key policy actions listed in the Policy Forum and the white paper has been developed for communication. The target audience for this brochure is broad in scope so that it may appeal to the wider thematic network community and wider society, at local, regional, national and international scales. The brochure is produced in digital format, in English, but consortium partners are encouraged to translate it into their own language.

<https://incredibleforest.net/policy-recommendations>

Manifesto of Alghero

This document is commitment to promote the contribution of non-wood forest products to an inclusive and green growth and eco-social progress in Europe and worldwide. The document puts forward the multifunctionality of the forests, proposes some key relevance benefits of NWFP, different implemented strategies, key issues to consider, weaknesses and threats related to NWFP, and call for actions proposed by stakeholders.

<https://incredibleforest.net/policy-recommendations>

8. INCREDIBLE innovations for NWFP

Selected outcomes and lessons learned in WP1 and WP3 have been developed into dissemination products tailored to priority target audiences.

The [Roadmap for innovating NWFP value chains](#) is targeting particularly practitioners and green entrepreneurs, both iNet members and non-members, through existing thematic network partners' dissemination channels and new mailing lists generated by the thematic network, as well as via the thematic network website and social media. A short summary document, iNet-specific, has been provided to all stakeholders and is available on-line on the website. It has been translated to local languages when it was considered necessary.

1. Promoting the INCREDIBLE achievements which have the most impact and are the result of an international collaboration;
2. Showing flagship initiatives that INCREDIBLE has promoted but that have not been fully developed (because they were beyond thematic network's tasks) which could be "adopted" by other organisations to complete its development or implementation (a kind of call to inherit INCREDIBLE by third parties when finished).

<https://incredibleforest.net/inet/cork>

<https://incredibleforest.net/inet/resins>

<https://incredibleforest.net/inet/aromatic-medicinal-plants>

<https://incredibleforest.net/inet/mushrooms-and-truffles>

<https://incredibleforest.net/inet/wild-nuts-and-berries>

NWFP start-ups: During the acceleration service (T3.2.2) provided to winners of the open innovation challenge, winners were supported by experts to create diverse materials for presenting their start-up, such as cards, leaflets, etc. These materials will be used by these start-ups to communicate their activities, but also be disseminated to business and entrepreneurial stakeholders and forest-related stakeholders as inspirational examples of innovations on NWFP supported by the thematic network INCREDIBLE.

https://www.incredibleforest.net/sites/default/files/resource/files/nfwps_oic_asv3.pdf

Factsheets and practice abstracts developed by iNet members (D2.1) provide innovative knowledge and easily accessible end-user material targeting both practitioners and the research community involved in all aspects of NWFP value chains. The 257 factsheets are stored in the [Knowledge repository for Non-Wood Forest Products](#), and their respective practice abstracts (one per factsheet) can be found in [EIP-Agri Projects site](#).

As a dissemination product, these factsheets have been grouped into 5 booklets (one per iNet) structured under several thematic indexes, available at the INCREDIBLE website.

https://www.incredibleforest.net/sites/default/files/resource/files/factsheet_index_cork.pdf

https://www.incredibleforest.net/sites/default/files/resource/img/factsheet_index_resin.pdf

https://www.incredibleforest.net/sites/default/files/resource/files/factsheet_index_amps.pdf

https://www.incredibleforest.net/sites/default/files/resource/files/factsheet_index_wmt.pdf

https://www.incredibleforest.net/sites/default/files/resource/files/factsheet_index_wnb.pdf

Lessons learnt

In order to support the animation of the iNets and the stakeholder interactions, the INCREDIBLE thematic network included a community of practice (COP). The INCREDIBLE COP is a platform where coordinators and local contact points from all five iNets meet, share experiences and discuss approaches for the next steps.

This report sets out how the INCREDIBLE COP has operated, and how it supported both the iNet operations and intra-iNet exchanges (between different regions of the same iNet) as well as cross-iNet exchanges. The activities of the COP are documented, explaining how these contributed to the INCREDIBLE objectives. Furthermore, the report also covers the use of the tools and instruments that have been introduced to support the iNets.

Finally, this report also includes recommendations and lessons learnt with respect to facilitating innovation in NWFP.

https://www.incredibleforest.net/sites/default/files/resource/files/nfwps_handbook_lessonslearnt.pdf

9. INCREDIBLE Green Tales

This product shows a wide collection of audio-visual material which include social, business and technological innovations and success stories via written or audio-visual testimonials bundled in

coherent narratives. To spread these Green Tales, some of these videos have been showed at the Policy Forum and Final Conference events.

A YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCBvxcdhNQQz2iySdJGsaHw>) has been created to host these materials and an easy access from the thematic network website has been developed to increase their visibility.

<https://incredibleforest.net/green-tales>

10. Publications

INCREDIBLE published short articles sectoral and practitioners' magazines/journals across the region (at least one for each iNet). Articles targeted at a broader audience (e.g. blogs or web-stories) were prepared on a regular basis. The information about these articles and provided links are included in the D4.3 *Project publication "Knowledge in practice"*.

<https://incredibleforest.net/deliverables>

11. Detected research needs for non-wood forest products in the Mediterranean

Emerging from the iNets, the research needs particularly consider Mediterranean NWFP in the context of a sustainable and socially inclusive bio-economy and the green economy. During the three years and a half of the thematic network INCREDIBLE (2017-2021), hundreds of stakeholders from Portugal, Spain, France, Italy, Croatia, Greece and Tunisia attended the different events held by the thematic network and expressed the research needs that are collected in this document.

https://www.incredibleforest.net/sites/default/files/resource/files/incredible_detected_research_needs_for_nwfp.pdf

12. Final Conference

On 15-16 April 2021, the INCREDIBLE thematic network celebrated its [Final Conference](#) (on-line). The event, co-organised by the European Forest Institute (EFI) and Instituto Superior de Agronomia, Universidade de Lisboa (ISA), explore and celebrate during 3 sessions the outcomes of the thematic network with a special emphasis on the flagship initiatives and important achievements of each Interregional iNet.

<https://www.incredibleforest.net/content/incredible-final-conference-building-partnerships-innovation-mediterranean-nwfp-value-chains>